

Portable, reproducible and scalable bioinformatics workflows using Nextflow and Pawsey Nimbus Cloud

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What's in this section?

- Bioinformatics workflows are complex
- Workflow management systems can help...
- Nextflow as a workflow manager

A typical bioinformatics workflow (rnaseq)

Biological samples/Library preparation

Raw sequence reads

Reads QC

Trimming

Reads QC

Alignment

Raw read counts associated with genes

Differential expression analysis

Functional interpretation

Simple? 😊

OR... Not so much 😞

Bioinformatics workflows

- Bioinformatics workflows are multi-step methods that are performed to process or analyse data.
- These are often comprised of multiple independent tools
- Issues with tool installation are common (incompatibilities, dependencies and version-related errors)

Bioinformatics workflows

- Large data size and many samples
- Generate hundreds of small files
- How to optimise compute resources?

Quantifying Reproducibility in Computational Biology: The Case of the Tuberculosis Drugome

Daniel Garijo, Sarah Kinnings, Li Xie, Lei Xie, Yinliang Zhang, Philip E. Bourne, Yolanda Gil

Published: November 27, 2013 • <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0080278>

Article	Authors	Metrics	Comments	Media Coverage
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More than 280 hours are required to reproduce the results of a typical computational biology paper...
~ 2 months!!!

Figure 1: Nextflow enables stable analyses on different platforms.

From: [Nextflow enables reproducible computational workflows](https://www.nature.com/articles/nbt.3820)

<https://www.nature.com/articles/nbt.3820>

**Qualitative
assessment of
Reproducibility**

Have you experienced the following when trying to reproduce your scientific results?

- Re-run your own pipeline after a gap of say 6 months ?
- Allow your collaborator to use your pipeline to run their datasets ?
 - On their own local machine
 - On a national computing infrastructure
- Allow a reviewer who is highly excited about your results but they want to systematically re-run your code on their side?

Workflow management systems

- Workflow managers provide a framework to co-ordinate and manage the execution of commands (bash/python/perl/other).
- They simplify the design and execution of workflows.
- They can implement efficient software management (e.g. Containers) and solve issues pertaining to software installations and execution.

Researcher can focus on the functionality of the pipeline.

Available workflow managers

nextflow

Cromwell

... and many more

Why Nextflow?

- Nextflow is very popular in the research community.
It is open source and has very active developer community.
- It has **nf-co.re**: a set of pre-developed but customisable bioinformatics pipelines
- It has **Nextflow-tower**: Provides a point and click web interface to launch any nextflow workflow on a connected compute infrastructure (e.g. AWS, Azure, institutional HPC)
- Nextflow can be used by developers to build custom workflows.
Sarah Beecroft will touch upon this in the later half of the the webinar.

Nextflow features

Scalability

- Your laptop might be enough to analyse a sample or two, but how to deal with hundreds of samples?
- Hardware requirements increased by orders of magnitude
- Ramp up from local machine to a high-end processor

Reproducibility

- If analyses are repeated are the outcomes the same?
 - in future
 - on other systems (portability)
 - by other people (collaboration)
- Are you able to track your data/tool `versions` through the analyses (provenance)

Productivity

- Run the same workflow on different compute infrastructures (e.g. your local machine, high performance computer, commercial cloud, etc).
- Is it possible to reduce installation/deployment time?
- Easier to maintain/modify/re-use
 - Tricky with plain scripting languages e.g. bash

Other interesting Nextflow features

Checkpointing: Enable re-execution of failed or changed tasks

Reporting: Generate plots of your workflow timelines
Generate compute usage reports

Community supported and maintained workflows: nf-co.re

Intermediate – beginner CLI friendly: Nextflow Tower (launch, manage, monitor via web interface)

The screenshot shows the nf-core website homepage. At the top is a navigation bar with links for Home, Pipelines, Modules, Tools, Docs, Events, and About. Below the navigation bar is the nf-core logo, which consists of the text 'nf-core' in green and black, and a stylized green apple core icon. Underneath the logo is the text: 'A community effort to collect a curated set of analysis pipelines built using Nextflow.' A large green button with the text 'VIEW PIPELINES' is centered below this text. Below the button is a search bar with the placeholder text 'Search' and a 'Search' button. At the bottom of the page, there is a green bar with three categories and their respective counts: 'Released 33', 'Under development 26', and 'Archived 5'.

- **nf.co-re** is a repository of community developed, supported, maintained nextflow pipelines
- 69 pipelines are currently available as part of nf-core
- Most of these pipeline are related to bioinformatics

Nextflow (nf-co.re) turns many steps into just a few

Pipeline summary

1. Download FastQ files via SRA, ENA or GEO ids and auto-create input samplesheet ([ENA FTP](#) ; *if required*)
2. Merge re-sequenced FastQ files ([cat](#))
3. Read QC ([FastQC](#))
4. UMI extraction ([UMI-tools](#))
5. Adapter and quality trimming ([Trim Galore!](#))
6. Removal of ribosomal RNA ([SortMeRNA](#))
7. Choice of multiple alignment and quantification routes:
 1. [STAR](#) -> [featureCounts](#)
 2. [STAR](#) -> [RSEM](#)
 3. [HiSAT2](#) -> [featureCounts](#)
8. Sort and index alignments ([SAMtools](#))
9. UMI-based deduplication ([UMI-tools](#))
10. Duplicate read marking ([picard MarkDuplicates](#))
11. Transcript assembly and quantification ([StringTie](#))
12. Create bigWig coverage files ([BEDTools](#) , [bedGraphToBigWig](#))
13. Extensive quality control:
 1. [RSeQC](#)
 2. [Qualimap](#)
 3. [dupRadar](#)
 4. [Preseq](#)
 5. [DESeq2](#)
14. Pseudo-alignment and quantification ([Salmon](#) ; *optional*)
15. Present QC for raw read, alignment, gene biotype, sample similarity, and strand-specificity checks ([MultiQC](#) , [R](#))


```
nextflow run nf-core/rnaseq \  
  --input samplesheet.csv \  
  --outdir <OUTDIR> \  
  --genome GRCh37 \  
  -profile <docker/singularity/podman/conda/institute>
```

Biological samples/Library preparation

Raw sequence reads

Reads QC

Trimming

Reads QC

Alignment

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Functional interpretation

Useful output logs from Nextflow

Workflow timeline

- An HTML timeline for all processes executed in your pipeline.
- Each bar represents a process run in the pipeline execution.
- Bar length represents the task duration time (wall-time).
- Bar colours are used to identify those tasks belonging to the same process.
- The numbers on the x-axis represent the time in absolute units eg. minutes, hours, etc.

CPU usage

nextflow.config

- When a pipeline script is launched, Nextflow looks for a configuration file
- It is a simple text file containing a set of properties defined using the syntax

name = value

```
// Resource allocation for various processes
/// Here you can be provide CPU and memory for all or various processes
/// Defining it as a parameter means users can customise/override when running the command

params.cpus = 1 // you'll need to include this parameter in your process. See process1.nf for example.

// Name containers to be used. For example:
// container_samtools = "quay.io/biocontainers/samtools:1.14--hb421002_0"
```

```
// resume pipeline from last successful process
resume = true
```

```
// Produce a workflow diagram
dag {
  enabled = true
  file = 'runInfo/dag.svg'
}

report {
  enabled = true
  file = 'runInfo/report.html'
}

timeline {
  enabled = true
  file = 'runInfo/timeline.html'
}

trace {
  enabled = true
  file = 'runInfo/trace.txt'
}
```

Containers

- Containers ‘package’ a set of software tools for reuse
- The container can be run on:
 - any hardware
 - any OS
 - any location
 - any user

... and more

Running the nfcore-rnaseq pipeline on a Nimbus VM instance

A single command ...

```
base_path=/cvmfs/data.biocommons.aarnet.edu.au/Final_resources_250722

nextflow run $base_path/nfcore_pipeline/rnaseq/ \
  --input samplesheet.csv \
  -profile singularity \
  --fasta $base_path/Mouse_references/genome.fa \
  --gtf $base_path/Mouse_references/Mmus.gtf \
  --star_index $base_path/Mouse_references/STARIndex_sarekGenome/ \
  --max_memory '30 GB' --max_cpus 2 \
  --outdir results \
  -with-report excecution_report.html \
  -with-timeline timeline_report.html \
  -with-dag flowchart.png
```


What's under the hood?

Introduction to Nextflow Development

What's in this section?

- Nextflow jargon
- Example Bash pipeline translated to Nextflow
- What's main.nf and nextflow.config?
- Nimbus: When, Why and How

Nextflow Jargon Primer

Nextflow has some specific terms:

- **Input data**
 - E.g. fastq files
- **Process/Job step**
 - E.g. Merge & QC
- **Intermediate files**
 - E.g. Contigs
- **Data channels**
 - Data/files piped between processes
- **Final output(s)**
 - E.g. VCF

Bash script: A short pipeline

Blast.sh

```
1  #!/bin/bash
2
3  #Set variable names
4  input_data="/some/data/sample.fa"
5  ref_database="/some/path/pdb"
6
7
8  # Run commands
9  # PROCESS ONE: blast search
10 blastp -db $ref_database -query $input_data -outfmt 6 > blast_result
11 cat blast_result | head -n 10 | cut -f 2 > top_hits.txt
12
13 # PROCESS TWO: extract top hits
14 # Note that top_hits.txt was created in PROCESS ONE, and is now used in PROCESS TWO
15 blastdbcmd -db $ref_database -entry_batch top_hits.txt > sequences.txt
16
```

Bash script vs Nextflow

Blast.sh

```
1  #!/bin/bash
2
3  #Set variable names
4  input_data="/some/data/sample.fa"
5  ref_database="/some/path/pdb"
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14 # Note that top_hits.txt was created in PROCESS ONE, and is now used i
15 blastdbcmd -db $ref_database -entry_batch top_hits.txt > sequences.txt
16
```

main.nf

```
1  #!/usr/bin/env nextflow
2
3  // Script parameters
4  params.input_data = "/some/data/sample.fa"
5  params.ref_database = "/some/path/pdb"
6
7  ref_database = file(params.ref_database)
8  input_data_ch = Channel.fromPath(params.input_data)
9
10 process blastSearch {
11     input:
12         file input_data from input_data_ch
13
14     output:
15         file "top_hits.txt" into top_hits_ch
16
17     """
18     blastp -db $ref_database -query $input_data -outfmt 6 > blast_result
19     cat blast_result | head -n 10 | cut -f 2 > top_hits.txt
20     """
21 }
22
23 process extractTopHits {
24     input:
25         file top_hits from top_hits_ch
26
27     output:
28         file "sequences.txt" into sequences_ch
29
30     """
31     blastdbcmd -db $db -entry_batch $top_hits > sequences.txt
32     """
33 }
34
```

Nextflow Concepts

Two files per workflow

Main.nf
(Script file)

The 'what'
-Commands
-Pipeline flow
-Parameters

```
1 #!/usr/bin/env nextflow
2
3 // Script parameters
4 params.input_data = "/some/data/sample.fa"
5 params.ref_database = "/some/path/pdb"
6
7 ref_database = file(params.ref_database)
8 input_data_ch = Channel.fromPath(params.input_data)
9
10 process blastSearch {
11     input:
12         file input_data from input_data_ch
13
14     output:
15         file "top_hits.txt" into top_hits_ch
16
17     """
18     blastp -db $ref_database -query $input_data -outfmt 6 > blast_result
19     cat blast_result | head -n 10 | cut -f 2 > top_hits.txt
20     """
21 }
22
23 process extractTopHits {
24     input:
25         file top_hits from top_hits_ch
26
27     output:
28         file "sequences.txt" into sequences_ch
29
30     """
31     blastdbcmd -db $db -entry_batch $top_hits > sequences.txt
32     """
33 }
34
```

Nextflow.config
(Configuration)

The 'how'
-Which software
-Settings

Nextflow Config: Customise how your pipeline runs

What can I set in the config file?

- Resume from where the pipeline crashed
- Which software to use
 - Conda
 - Containers
 - Versions
- CPU/Memory usage
- Singularity/Docker/Podman/Charlie Cloud options
- Logging options
- Many more...

Nextflow.config

```
1 // Resume where pipeline failed
2 resume = true
3
4 //Set up a profile for Nimbus
5 profiles {
6   nimbus {
7     workDir = "$MYSCRATCH/nxf_work"
8     process {
9       cache = 'lenient'
10      stageInMode = 'symlink'
11    }
12
13    withName: 'extractTopHits' {
14      cpus = 4
15      time = '1d'
16      memory = '120GB'
17    }
18  }
19 }
```

Nimbus Cloud Compute @ Pawsey

What is Nimbus?

If you are an Australian researcher or scientist, Nimbus is **NO CHARGE** for you to use

Choose Your Compute Size

n3.1c4r	1 core	4GB RAM
n3.2c8r	2 cores	8GB RAM
n3.4c16r	4 cores	16GB RAM
n3.8c32r	8 cores	32GB RAM
n3.16c64r	16 cores	64GB RAM

When to Use Nimbus

Special features for bioinformatics users!

Nimbus BioImage

Designed to make life easier for bioinformatics users

- Pre-installed software highlights
 - Nextflow, Singularity, Docker, Pip, Python3, R
- Run R-studio and Jupyter Notebook
- Common dependencies already installed
- CernVM-FS- a read-only file system for accessing reference datasets

Applying for Nimbus

Application Title *

Give the application a title

Your work *

Characters: 0/1024

A short description of your research

How many n3.1c4r (1 core and 4 GB RAM) instances?

Add the number of instances of this particular flavour you would like

How many n3.2c8r (2 core and 8 GB RAM) instances?

Add the number of instances of this particular flavour you would like

How many n3.4c16r (4 core and 16 GB RAM) instances?

Add the number of instances of this particular flavour you would like

How many n3.8c32r (8 core and 32 GB RAM) instances?

Add the number of instances of this particular flavour you would like

How many n3.16c64r (16 core and 64 GB RAM) would you like?

Add the number of instances of this particular flavour you would like

GPU resources

Characters: 0/1024

Please visit <https://support.pawsey.org.au/documentation/display/US/Nimbus+GPU+Access> to determine whether these resources would meet your requirements. Note these are limited and have strict time limits. If so, please list the number and type required.

Volume storage *

Characters: 0/64

Please state the amount of data volume storage you require in GB. This is working storage that you attach to your instance i.e. input and output files and is not for long-term storage. Please back-up externally. [Learn more here](#) - <https://support.pawsey.org.au/documentation/display/US/Manage+a+Data+Volume>

Acacia storage

Each project will be allocated Acacia storage of 1000 GB [1TB] automatically. You can request up to 10 000GB [10TB] here. Over this amount you will need to make a separate Managed Storage application via the application portal. Details on Acacia here - <https://support.pawsey.org.au/documentation/display/US/Acacia++User+Guide>

Help?

- I am unsure which flavour/instance type best suits my research needs. I would like to talk to a specialist. Example case studies (<https://support.pawsey.org.au/documentation/display/US/How+to+Choose+a+Flavour>)

Additional details

Characters: 0/1024

If appropriate, please enter any additional project details or queries that may be related to this application

FOR codes *

ABS Field of Research codes

Percentage

%

Total

0

%

[+ Add a new line](#)

You can add lines as much as you need, but the total of the percentages must equal 100.

Grant funding number

Characters: 0/1024

Please include any relevant grant funding number. If none, please write None or N/A

1st condition of use *

- I agree to notify Pawsey if the owner changes

2nd condition of use *

- I agree to notify Pawsey if my email address changes

3rd condition of use *

- I agree that my project allocation is limited to 6 months and at the end of that period, I will submit a short report on the outcomes of my project and my experience with using Nimbus. If I want continued use, I must re-apply for an allocation.

4th condition of use *

- I understand that my data and instance(s) will be deleted from Nimbus after a one month grace period, if I do not re-apply before the end of my 6-month allocation

* Mandatory Field

Previous

1

Next

References

Topic	Link
nf-core	https://nf-co.re/
Nextflow training	https://training.seqera.io/

Thank you!